

Synthesis of Some New 4(3H)Quinazolinones as CNS Depressants and Antifungal Agents

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Manuscript received 17 June 1983, revised 3 July 1984, accepted 27 April 1985

Several new 6,8-dichloro-2-phenyl-3[(substituted)benzothiazol-2'-yl]-4(3H)quinazolinones have been synthesised and screened for their CNS depressant activity. Their fungicidal activity has also been screened on *Aspergillus niger* and *Alternaria alternata* at two dilutions. The antifungal screening of compounds reveals that some of them inhibit fungal growth.

DIVERSE biological activities have been encountered in compounds having the quinazolinone ring system¹. 4(3H)Quinazolinones with CNS depressant activity² are known and 2-methyl-3-*o*-tolyl-4(3H)quinazolinone³ has been utilised in therapy as a hypnotic and sedative; other quinazolinones have been found to possess muscle relaxant, antiinflammatory⁴, antitubercular^{5,6}, antihistaminic⁷ and hypotensive⁸ activities.

In view the wide spectrum activities of this system it was considered worthwhile to synthesise some 4(3H)quinazolinones as CNS depressant and antifungal agents. The compounds were synthesised according to the scheme outlined.

Experimental

The melting points were taken in open capillary in liquid bath and are uncorrected. A Perkin-Elmer 399B for ir and a Coleman analyser for elemental analysis were used.

3,5-Dichloroanthranilic acid was prepared by a known method⁹. Benzoyl derivative of 3,5-dichloroanthranilic acid was prepared by the method of Vogel¹⁰.

2-Amino-substituted benzothiazoles: 2-Amino-substituted benzothiazoles were prepared by the oxidation of asymmetrical aryl thioureas with liquid bromine in chloroform¹¹.

6,8-Dichloro-2-phenyl-3-[(6'-chloro)benzothiazol-2'-yl]-4(3H)quinazolinone: A mixture of 3,5-dichloro-N-benzoylanthranilic acid (1 g), 2-amino-6-chloro-benzothiazole (0.54 g) and pyridine (20 ml) was

refluxed for 6 h at 115°. It was cooled and poured into 5 N HCl (75 ml) to get the required product. It was filtered, washed with 5% sodium bicarbonate solution and distilled water, dried and recrystallised from ethanol to get 6,8-dichloro-2-phenyl-3-[(6'-chloro)-benzothiazol-2'-yl]-4(3H)quinazolinone (37%), m.p. 184° (Found: C, 44.71; H, 2.31 C₂₁H₁₀Cl₂N₂OS calcd. C, 44.8; H, 2.44%); ν_{max} (nujol) 1640(s) 1465(m), 1380(s), 1210(m), 1165(s), 840(s) and 730(s) cm⁻¹.

Similarly, other 6,8-dichloro-2-phenyl-3-[(substituted)benzothiazol-2'-yl]-4(3H)quinazolinones were synthesised. Their yields, melting points and analytical data are recorded in Table 1.

Pharmacological screening: The compounds 6,8-dichloro-2-phenyl-3-[(substituted)benzothiazol-2'-yl]-4(3H)quinazolinones were screened for antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger* and *Alternaria alternata* by the agar diffusion technique¹² at two dilutions. The percentage inhibition of growth was determined by comparison with growth in controls and the results are recorded in Table 1. All solutions were prepared in absolute alcohol. The medium in controls and treated plates was potato dextrose agar culture medium and the incubation time was 96 h at 26 ± 1°.

Results and Discussion

The results indicate that the activity of the compounds is of considerable extent against both the species. The replacement of hydrogen by methyl or chloro group increases the activity at both the dilutions. Fungicidal action decreases when the substituent is methoxy and ethoxy. The results are compared with a well known fungicide, sodium pentachlorophenate (NaPCP).

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TABLE I—FUNGICIDAL ACTIVITY OF 6 8-DICHLORO-2-PHENYL-3[(SUBSTITUTED)BENZOTHAZOL-2'-YL]-4 (3H)QUINAZOLINONES*

Sl. no.	Substituents X	Molecular formula	Yield %	M p. °C	% Inhibition			
					<i>A. alternata</i>		<i>A. niger</i>	
					1:1500	1:3500	1:1500	1:3500
1.	H	C ₂₁ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	59	209	100	42	36	20
2.	5-Me	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	71	170	64	48	66	35
3.	6-Me	C ₂₁ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	85	180	59	40	50	32
4.	4-Cl	C ₂₁ H ₁₀ Cl ₃ N ₂ O ₂ S	60	188	100	79	80	71
5.	5-Cl	C ₂₁ H ₁₀ Cl ₃ N ₂ O ₂ S	46	151	66	61	73	54
6.	4-OMe	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₃ S	48	132	58	39	76	36
7.	6-OMe	C ₂₁ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₃ S	55	194	64	51	86	58
8.	6-OEt	C ₂₃ H ₁₅ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₃ S	40	164	57	44	64	51
9.	NaPCP				100	100	100	100

* Analytical data for carbon and hydrogen agreed with the calculated values within the limit of experimental error.

Some of the synthesised compounds were tested for central nervous system depressant activity on mice. Analgesic activity, maximum electroseizure, antireserpine and anorexigenic tests were also performed. All the compounds were administered intraperitoneally to a group of mice in various different doses.

The compounds are relatively non-toxic. All the tested compounds depressed spontaneous motor activity at all the doses. The depression being maximum in compounds 1, 2 and 3 at 464, 215, 100, 63.2, and 46.4 i.p., respectively. Ataxia was also observed in compounds 2 and 4 at 464, 215, and 1000 i.p., respectively. Some of the compounds showed hypothermic action at different doses. Hyperthermic was recorded only in compound 1 at 63.2 i.p. There was a slight change in body temperature in compounds 1, 2, 3 and 4 at different doses. Anoxia was also performed in compounds 1, 2 and 3 at 464 i.p., writhing and gasping were also observed in compounds 4 and 5 at different doses. These compounds were also tested for antitremorine activity but the results showed no significant change.

From the results it is evident that the tested compounds showed analgesic and anorexigenic activity at lower doses. The compound 5 did not show anorexigenic property. Maximum electroseizure was also observed at lower dose. All the compounds were screened for their *in vivo* monoamine oxidase inhibitory activity against reserpine induced activity.

The conclusion derived from the above discussion is that the tested compounds exhibited mild to moderate CNS depressant action and various other activities. They have both stimulating and depressive activities.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the Director, C.D.R.I., Lucknow for pharmacological screening, the authorities of D.A.V. (P.G.) College, Dehra Dun for providing facilities and the C.S.I.R., New Delhi for Senior Research Fellowship to one of us (A.K.S.).

References

1. W. L. F. ARMAREGO, *Advan. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1963, 1, 253.
2. A. SOULAIRAE and C. L. CROLLESMANN, *Life Sci.*, 1967, 6 1229.
3. A. RAVINA, *Presse Med.*, 1959, 67, 891.
4. J. OSSELACRE, F. G. PEEERRE and A. L. C. LAPIERE, Ger. Pat. 2705454 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1978, 88, 6932).
5. P. N. BHARGAVA and H. SINGH, *Indian J. Pharm.*, 1969, 31, 111.
6. K. S. L. SRIVASTAVA, *Indian J. Pharm.*, 1970, 32, 97.
7. S. HAZAO, H. J. HAVERA and W. G. STRYCHER, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1969, 12, 936.
8. G. RE P. DA BONOLA, M. J. MAGSTRETT, E. MESSARAN and I. SETAKAR, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1968, 11, 1136.
9. A. S. WHEELER and W. M. OATES, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 32, 770.
10. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", 4th ed., E.L.B.S., 1978, p 884.
11. A. HUGERSHOFF, *Chem. Ber.*, 1903, 36, 3134.
12. J. G. HORSEFALL, *Bot. Rev.*, 1945, 11, 357.